

EFFECTS OF PORES AND VOIDS ON THE INTERLAMINAR DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS OF A CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITE

Leif E. Asp and Fredrik Brandt

*The Aeronautical Research Institute of Sweden
P.O. Box 11021, SE-161 11 Bromma, Sweden*

SUMMARY: Presence of pores and voids is known to impair mechanical properties such as strengths and moduli of composite materials. At least, for aeronautical applications it is important to understand how defects such as voids affect the interlaminar delamination toughness of a composite laminate. Therefore an investigation on the influence of voids on the interlaminar delamination toughness of a carbon fiber/epoxy composite in pure modes I and II as well as mixed mode has been performed. Voids are found to have a deleterious or no effect on the critical strain energy release rate at crack growth initiation. However, at propagation in pure mode I and mixed mode load-cases presence of voids causes a R-curve behavior. The increase in G_c , which is strong in mode I and moderate in mixed mode is inherent to changes in failure mechanisms. In pure mode I, ply splits are observed to bridge the crack as the crack locally leaps between plies at propagation. In mixed mode ($G_{II}/G \approx 0.5$), the crack propagates in one interface only, multilayer cracking in the crack tip region results in increased G_c at crack propagation. From the observed R-curve behavior it is concluded that pores and voids do not impair the delamination toughness of the HTA/6376C composite in static loading.

KEYWORDS: Voids, pores, manufacturing defects, interlaminar delamination toughness, delamination tests.

INTRODUCTION

Poor manufacturing of laminates may cause appearance of voids and pores in and in-between plies. To date, laminates containing detectable voids are discarded. Cost will be significantly reduced if laminates containing voids can be accepted in some applications. For this reason it is important to understand the influence of voids on the mechanical properties of composite laminates. In particular, for aeronautical applications, the effect of voids on interlaminar delamination toughness is of interest. This is motivated by interlaminar delamination growth being one of the major failure modes in composite structures, such as aircraft wing skins. Interlaminar delamination or fracture may be defined as debonding of plies due to the interlaminar stresses present in the laminate.

It is well known that voids degrade mechanical properties, e.g. tensile and shear strengths, of composites. Over the years a number of studies have been presented on this matter. Comprehensive reviews on the work in this area have been given by Judd and Wright [1], and more recently by Cantwell and Morton [2]. To date, work has been focused on the effects of void content on strengths and moduli of composites. Especially, the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) has been of concern [1-4]. Results presented on the effects of voids and pores

on mechanical properties are found to differ substantially between studies. For instance, for carbon fiber/epoxy composites, the ILSS has been reported to decrease between 1 and 21% for the first one percent voids [1]. This inconsistency is coherent with the difficulty to measure true void content reported by Ghiorse [5]. In spite of the efforts made, to the authors knowledge, no results on the influence of voids on the interlaminar delamination toughness of CF/EP composites have been reported in the literature.

The objective of this study is to investigate the influence of voids and pores on the interlaminar delamination toughness of a HTA/6376C composite laminate in pure modes I and II as well as mixed mode loading.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Test methods

Fig. 1: FFA's mixed mode bending rig

To study the effects of pores and voids on delamination toughness of HTA/6376C composite laminates, several test methods were utilized. Tests in modes I and II as well as mixed mode were performed. For Mode I, the common DCB (Double Cantilever Beam) test was used. In mode II, specimens were tested in three-point bending in the ENF (End Notch Flexural) test. Finally, in the mixed mode tests, the specimens were tested under combined loads in the MMB (Mixed Mode Bending) test. Seven specimens were tested in each test method. All tests were performed in a modified version of the mixed mode rig originally suggested by Reeder and Crews [6,7]. In this study only one mixed mode ratio was investigated together with the pure mode tests. According to the analysis by Reeder and Crews [6], an expected mode ratio, G_{II}/G , of 0.5 was chosen by setting $c=41$ mm, where $L=50$ mm, see Fig. 1.

Three-point bending tests were performed to determine the flexural modulus of the uncracked laminates at room temperature. In these experiments the distance between support rollers was 65 mm. All experiments were performed at ambient conditions.

Specimens

All specimens were fabricated from HTA/6376C carbon/epoxy prepreg supplied by Ciba Geigy. The laminates were cured according to the suppliers recommendations (at 6 bars pressure). However, to introduce voids in one of the laminates the applied vacuum was tampered with during cure. This was done in the following manner: General consolidation of the laminate was achieved as the vacuum-bag was evacuated prior to curing. After evacuation the vacuum pump was turned off. The laminate was heated at a rate of 2°C/min to a temperature of 175°C. As the laminate was heated the pressure inside the bag rose to 6 bar. When the laminate had been heated for one hour the bag was ventilated at 1 atmosphere pressure. Ventilation was repeated as the temperature reached the plateau value of 175°C. After one hour at 175°C the laminate was left at a pressure of 1 atmosphere.

The laminates included a 35 mm long artificial delamination as a starter crack. The artificial delamination consisted of a 7.5 µm thick Upilex 7.5S polyimide film from UBE. The thin film used reduces the resin pocket created at the film edge and hence its influence on the critical strain energy release rate [8]. After curing, the laminates were C-scanned for flaws, such as delaminations, and cut into specimens in a diamond wheel cutter. Prior to testing all specimens were dried in an oven at 70°C for two weeks. The dimensions of the rectangularly shaped specimens were; width 20 mm, length 150 mm and nominal thickness 3.3 mm. The nominal thickness of the void-free laminate was 3.1 mm. The specimen lay-up was $[0^{\circ}_{12}/\text{//}(\pm 5^{\circ}/0^{\circ}_4)_s]$, where the sign “//” refers to the interface plane, i.e. the plane of the artificial delamination. The off-axis angle of 5° was applied to reduce fiber bridging at delamination growth. In a study by Olsson et al. [8] it was concluded that an off-axis layer at the interface suppresses fiber bridging in DCB and MMB tests. Also, Olsson et al. [8] showed that the off-axis layers in the composite have a negligible effect on the local G distribution through the specimen width. To release any adhesion between the polyimide film and the composite the specimens were pre-loaded prior to testing.

Three-point bend specimens were cut to the dimensions; width 5 mm and length 75 mm with a nominal thickness of 3.3 mm.

Measurements

The delamination beam DCB, ENF and MMB tests were performed in a screw-driven Zwick tension load machine at a constant displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. In the DCB tests a 250 N load cell was used, while in the ENF and MMB tests a 5 kN load cell was utilized. The specimens were connected to the test rig by hinges with automatic couplings, for details see ref. 7.

Crack growth in the DCB, MMB and ENF specimens was measured manually with a traveling microscope. The microscope was equipped with an instrumented dial gauge providing continuous reading of the observed crack tip position. The dial gauge had a maximum stroke length of 20 mm. In the DCB tests, use of a 20 mm extension made it possible to measure a total crack growth length of 40 mm. Mode I opening displacement in the DCB test was measured with a string/wheel potentiometer drawn by a wire attached to the load point of the specimen. In the ENF and three point bend tests the vertical load point displacement was measured with an instrumented dial gauge. In the mixed mode MMB test, the vertical fulcrum displacement, d_c , as well as the opening displacement, d_I , were measured with instrumented dial gauges, see Fig. 1. The vertical fulcrum displacement was measured

directly on the specimen, whereas the opening displacement was measured on an extension of the upper hinge in the direction of the applied load. In the experiments loads, displacements and crack lengths were acquired with an IBM PC equipped with Labtech Notebook software.

The void content was determined by image analysis, using the OPTILAB[®] image analysis software of Graftek. The void content of the composite was averaged over 36 cross-sections covering the entire area (20*3.3 mm²) of totally 20 specimens. Interlaminar void contents in 0°/+5° and +5°/-5° interlayers were determined separately in one dimension on the respective interface. The void content of the laminate was determined on specimens cut parallel as well as perpendicular to the 0°-direction, whereas interlaminar void contents were determined on specimens cut parallel to the 0°-direction, only.

DATA REDUCTION

Here, a short description of the methods used for the data reduction is given. A more complete description was presented in ref. 7. The methods used for evaluation of the DCB and ENF are based on load, displacement and crack length measurements. The results for the strain energy release rates for MMB load cases are achieved by superposition of the pure mode I and mode II load cases, see Figs. 2 and 3.

The mode I strain energy release rate was determined using an expression by Hashemi et al. [9],

$$G_I = \frac{3}{2} \frac{P_I d_I}{b(a + \Delta)} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1) b is the specimen width, a is the measured crack length and Δ is a crack length correction. Δ is determined analytically using an expression by Olsson [10] (the shear factor is set to $K=5/6$),

$$\frac{\Delta}{h} = \left(\frac{E_F}{12KG_T} + \sqrt{\frac{E_F}{6E_T}} \right) \frac{h}{a} + \sqrt[4]{\frac{E_F}{6E_T}} + \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{E_F}{G_T}} \quad (2)$$

The strain energy release rate in mode II was determined using the following expression by Carlsson and Gillespie [11]

$$G_{II} = \frac{9a^2 P_{II} d_{II}}{2b} \frac{\left(1 - C_{SH} \frac{P_{II}}{d_{II}} \right)}{(2L^3 + 3a^3)}, \text{ where } C_{SH} = \frac{6L + 3a - \frac{L^3}{a^2}}{20bhG_T} \quad (3).$$

In the equations presented, h is half the thickness of the specimen, E_F is the measured longitudinal flexural modulus. E_T and G_T are the transverse Young's and shear moduli, respectively. Here, data from the void-free laminate are used [7], $E_T=10.5$ GPa and $G_T=5.25$ GPa. Eqs. (1) and (3) have low sensitivity to the accuracy in estimations of these mechanical properties.

Fig. 2: Separation of modal loads in the MMB test

The results for the strain energy release rates for MMB load cases are achieved by superposition of the pure mode I and mode II load cases, see Figs. 2 and 3. The respective mode I, P_I , and mode II, P_{II} , load components, which have been worked out by Reeder and Crews [6], are proportional to the applied load, P , as:

$$P_I = \left(\frac{3c-L}{4L}\right)P \quad , \quad P_{II} = \left(\frac{c+L}{L}\right)P \quad (4)$$

where P , c and L are defined in Fig. 1. Further, geometry determines the displacements associated with mode I opening, d_I , and mode II flexure, d_{II} . The mode I opening displacement, d_I , is measured. The mode II displacement, d_{II} , is calculated from d_I and the fulcrum displacement, d_c , as

$$d_{II} = d_c + \Delta_c \quad , \quad \text{where } \Delta_c = d_I L \frac{1}{\sqrt{16L^2 - d_I^2}} \quad (5)$$

In the analysis of the three-point bend tests, determining the flexural modulus, influence of shear deformation was taken into account.

Fig. 3: Separation of modal displacements in the MMB test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The laminate void content was determined to 0.9%. The interlaminar void contents between the $0^\circ/+5^\circ$ (the position of the starter crack) and $+5^\circ/-5^\circ$ plies were 1.4% and 9.2%, respectively. The scatter in data is large as the voids were irregularly distributed in the laminate. For this reason some of the cross-sections contained a large amount of voids as others were void-free. The largest values for the void content of the laminate and interlaminar void content measured in one specimen were 2.2% and 25.8%, respectively. All the observed voids were needle shaped, meaning that they were long in the direction parallel to the fibers compared to their width. The length of the individual voids varied, whereas the void diameter was typically that of 1-2 fiber diameters.

The flexural modulus of the laminate containing voids was determined to 111 GPa, which is 7.5% lower than that previously measured flexural modulus of the void-free laminate [7]. This is in good agreement with results by Ghiorse [5], who reported a decrease in the flexural modulus of 5.3% for a carbon fiber/epoxy cross-ply laminate for the first one percent voids.

Delamination tests

Table 1: The critical strain energy release rates of the tests on the void-free and voided laminates. Standard deviations are presented within brackets. All units in J/m^2 .

Test method	Void-free laminate		voided laminate	
	G_C (initiation)	G_C (max)	G_C (initiation)	G_C (max)
DCB (mode I)	229.0 (± 17.8)	253.4 (± 6.6)	239.8 (± 9.7)	441.4 (± 50.8)
ENF (mode II)	883.1 (± 117.5)	883.1 (± 117.5)	811.3 (± 57.0)	811.3 (± 57.0)
MMB (mixed mode)	478.8 (± 43.7)	487.1 (± 45.5)	381.4 (± 47.6)	454.5 (± 70.3)

The results of the delamination tests are summarized in Table 1. In the table critical strain energy release rates, G_C , for void-free specimens and specimens containing voids, referred to as voided laminate, are presented. Table 1 lists data for G_C at crack growth initiation as well as maximum G_C at crack propagation. The maximum G_C provides information about the R-

curve behavior of the specimens, i.e. the dependency of the critical strain energy release rate on crack length. All data for void-free specimens were reported in a previous study [7]. In ref. 7 a more comprehensive description of the delamination crack growth behavior of the void-free specimens is given.

DCB tests

The presence of voids did not affect the critical strain energy release rate at crack growth initiation in pure mode I, see Table 1. However, their presence affected the crack growth behavior. Although stable crack growth was observed in both void-free specimens and specimens containing voids, their overall behavior were considerably different. For void-free specimens no R-curve behavior was found. In contrast, for specimens containing voids a very strong R-curve behavior was observed. Typical appearances of the critical strain energy release rates as a function of crack lengths are depicted in Fig. 4. For these specimens the critical strain energy release rate increased as the crack propagated. The maximum value at crack propagation was 84% higher than that at crack growth initiation, see Fig. 4. This shift in crack growth behavior is explained by a change in failure mechanism. In the void-free specimens an insignificant amount of crack bridging was established at the crack tip. In the specimens containing voids, however, ply splits (approximately 1-2 mm wide) were observed to bridge the crack. The bridged zone was measured to be 25-30 mm long. The observed crack bridging appeared as the crack tip locally leaped between plies as the crack propagated. The scatter in data for the laminate containing voids is significantly larger than for the void-free laminate, see Table 1. Thus, the irregularity in the distribution of voids affects the interlaminar delamination toughness of the composite loaded in pure mode I.

Fig.4: Schematic of the mode I critical strain energy release rates dependence on crack length for the void-free and void containing (voided) laminates

In a recent study, Hou et al. [12] reported results on the influence of voids on the interlaminar delamination toughness for CF/PEI woven fabric composites. In accordance to the results presented here, Hou et al. reported an increase in the value of the critical strain energy release rate at crack propagation with an increase in void content. However they found this increase in the energy release rate to originate in an enlarged crack tip region rather than in ply-

splitting. Due to the fiber architecture, no ply splits were reported to appear in the woven composites.

ENF tests

For both types of laminates the crack growth was unstable when loaded in pure mode II. In the ENF tests, presence of voids was found to have a slightly deleterious effect on the critical strain energy release rate. G_{IIC} at crack growth initiation was 8% lower for the laminate containing voids compared to the void-free one. To assure that the resin pocket created at the starter film tip did not affect the measured energy release rate, tests of four pre-cracked ENF specimens were performed. The specimens were pre-cracked in mode I until the starter crack length exceeded 37 mm. These tests confirmed the results, and hence any effect of the resin pocket was excluded. However, in these additional tests it was found that stable crack growth can be achieved as the initial crack length exceeds 37 mm. According to the analysis by Reeder and Crews [6] stable crack growth is expected for a crack length larger than 35 mm. Observations of the crack tip indicated that the crack propagated in one plane, only. As a consequence, no crack bridging was detected. This is coherent with observations reported for mode II tests on CF/PEI woven composites by Hou et al. [12].

MMB tests

Stable crack propagation was achieved in both laminates. In mixed mode loading the presence of voids was found to decrease the critical strain energy release rate at crack growth initiation by 20%. However, as the crack propagated the critical strain energy release rate increased and a R-curve behavior was recorded for the void containing specimens. Due to this R-curve behavior the recorded maximum strain energy release rate at propagation was at the same level for the two laminates. As in the DCB test results, the scatter in data, at propagation, for the laminate containing voids is larger than for the void-free laminate, see Table I. Crack bridging was not observed in either of the two laminates. As the crack propagated in the $0^\circ/5^\circ$ interface only, the recorded R-curve behavior of the laminate containing voids is explained by multiple crack planes at the crack tip. Multiple crack planes were observed on the edge of the specimens at crack propagation and in post-mortem optical microscopy.

The mode mixture in the MMB test deviated from the expected $G_{II}/G=0.5$. The achieved mode mixture was found to be 0.54 for the laminate containing voids as well as for the void-free laminate. These deviations from the expected mode mixture are due to the evaluation method used. Based on linear elasticity, methods based on load and load-displacement measurements should give the expected mode mixity of 0.5 [6]. In fact, load based methods give a mode mixture of 0.5. However, a previous investigation [7] revealed non-linear load-compliance relationships and indicated methods based on load-displacement measurements to be more accurate than methods based on load measurements only. For this reason, results based on load and displacement measurements only are reported here.

Dependency of delamination toughness on mode mixture

In Fig. 5 the critical strain energy release rates at crack growth initiation are presented as a function of mode mixture. To show trends, data points for void-free laminate and the laminate containing voids, marked voided laminate, have been curve fitted by interpolation.

The graph shows that presence of voids reduced the critical strain energy release rate at crack growth initiation in pure mode II and mixed mode ($G_{II}/G \approx 0.5$). In pure mode I, however, G_C was unaffected by the present voids. In contrast, at crack propagation, presence of voids most strongly affected the critical strain energy release rate in pure mode I.

Fig. 5: Critical strain energy release rate at crack growth initiation as a function of mode mixture. Interpolations between data points are included to show trends for the two laminates.

CONCLUSIONS

The influence of voids on the interlaminar delamination toughness of a carbon fiber/epoxy composite in pure modes I and II as well as mixed mode has been investigated. Voids were found to have a deleterious or no effect on the critical strain energy release rate at crack growth initiation. However, at propagation in pure mode I and mixed mode load-cases presence of voids was found increase G_C . This increase, which was found to be very strong in mode I and moderate in mixed mode, is inherent to changes in failure mechanisms. In pure mode I, ply splits were observed to bridge the crack as the crack locally leaped between plies at propagation. In mixed mode ($G_{II}/G \approx 0.5$), the crack propagated in one interface. However, multiple cracks observed at the crack tip and in front of the crack, resulted in an increased G_C at crack propagation in mixed mode loading. From the observed R-curve behavior it is concluded that pores and voids do not impair the delamination toughness of the HTA/6376C composite in static loading.

REFERENCES

1. Judd, N.C.W. and Wright, W.W., "Voids and their effects on the mechanical properties of composites- An appraisal", *SAMPE Journal*, **14**, 1978, pp. 10-14.
2. Cantwell, W.J. and Morton, J., "The significance of damage and defects and their detection in composite materials: A review", *J. strain analysis*, **27**, 1992, pp. 29-42.
3. Bowles, K.J. and Frimpong, S., "Void effects on the interlaminar shear strength of unidirectional graphite-fiber-reinforced composites", *J. Comp. Mat.*, **26**, 1992, pp. 1487-1509.
4. Wisnom, M.R., Reynolds, T. and Gwilliam, N., "Reduction in interlaminar shear strength by discrete and distributed voids", *Comp. Sci. Techn.*, **56**, 1996, pp. 93-101.
5. Ghiorse, S.R., "Effect of void content on the mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy laminates", *SAMPE Quart.*, 1993, pp. 54-59.
6. Reeder, J.R. and Crews, Jr, J.H., "Mixed-mode bending method for delamination testing", *AIAA Journal*, **28**, 1990, pp. 1270-1276.
7. Asp, L.E., "Moisture and temperature effects on the interlaminar delamination toughness of a carbon/epoxy composite", *FFA TN 1996-52*, The Aeronautical Research Institute of Sweden, 1996.
8. Olsson, R., Thesken, J.C., Brandt, F., Jönsson, N. and Nilsson, S., "Investigations of delamination criticality and the transferability of growth criteria", *FFA TN 1996-31*, The Aeronautical Research Institute of Sweden, 1996.
9. Hashemi, S., Kinloch, A.J. and Williams, J.G., "Corrections needed in double cantilever beam tests for assessing the interlaminar failure of fibre composites", *J. Mat. Sci. Lett.*, **8**, 1989, pp. 125-129.
10. Olsson, R., "A simplified improved beam analysis of the DCB specimen", *Comp. Sci. Techn.*, **43**, 1992, pp. 329-338.
11. Carlsson, L.A. and Gillespie, Jr., J.W., "Mode-II interlaminar fracture of composites", In *Application of fracture mechanics to composites*, K. Friedrich, Ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1989, pp. 113-158.
12. Hou, M., Ye, L. and Mai, Y.-W., "Effect of moulding temperature on flexure, impact strength and interlaminar fracture toughness of CF/PEI composite", *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.*, **15**, 1996, pp. 1117-1130.